

THE EFFECT OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON THE QUALITY OF RESIN INFUSED THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX PREPREG

P.K. Mallick and J. C. Ragone
Center for Lightweighting Automotive Materials and Processing
University of Michigan-Dearborn
4901 Evergreen Road, Dearborn, MI 48128, USA
pkm@umich.edu

SUMMARY

This paper presents the experiments conducted to determine the effects of process parameters, namely temperature, feed speed and transverse pressure, on the quality of a thermoplastic matrix prepreg produced by continuous resin infusion process. The prepreg quality was determined in terms of tensile strength and its variability. Based on the experiments, recommendations are made for selecting the process parameters that can produce good quality prepreg.

Keywords: Thermoplastic matrix composite, Resin infusion, Prepreg, Process parameters, Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Current thermoset matrix composites have long cycle times, which make them less competitive with other structural materials for large volume production in the automotive industry. A reduction in cycle time is necessary and one of the ways this can be accomplished is by using thermoplastic matrix composites. In addition to lower cycle times, thermoplastic matrix composites offer a number of other advantages over thermoset matrix composites. Thermoplastic matrix composites can be joined by a variety of welding techniques and they can be easily recycled. In general, they also have a higher resistance to brittle fracture than thermoset matrix composites. However, the use of thermoplastic matrix composites for structural automotive applications requires the development of low cost, high speed manufacturing processes. Continuous resin infusion is one such process and is the subject of this paper.

The resin infusion process utilizes a combination of heat and pressure to flow liquid thermoplastic resin through a dry fiber network in a short amount of time. Wang et al. [1] used a continuously running double belt process to manufacture thermoplastic composite prepregs. In this process, a multi-layer stack of dry fibers were impregnated by infusing layers of thermoplastic sheets at different temperatures, pressures and feed speeds. Macro-impregnation of the fabrics was accomplished easily, but the strong resistance of the individual yarns to transverse flow delayed the micro-impregnation significantly and produced strong inhomogeneity within the fabric layers. The mechanical properties and damage patterns were very sensitive to the level of micro-

impregnation. A second study done by Mayer et al. [2] examined the factors controlling the micro-impregnation of the individual yarns in orthotropic bidirectional fabrics. It was shown that micro-flow between the fibers is affected by the polymer viscosity, consolidation pressure, and the time the polymer is held above its melt temperature. An increased temperature and lower process velocity was found to be beneficial since it quickly lowers the viscosity of the polymer and allows more time for micro-flow to take place. The limiting factors were the merging of the flow fronts and void entrapment as the liquid polymer flow approached radially within the yarn.

This paper describes the experimental work conducted to produce thermoplastic matrix prepregs using continuous resin infusion technique. The process is comparable to the one studied by Wang, except in the technique used in this work, compression rollers were used instead of the double belt arrangement. In this technique, a single layer of dry fabric tape is sandwiched between two thin thermoplastic films and pulled continuously through a heating chamber where heat and pressure facilitate impregnation by resin infusion. Three pairs of rollers are used instead of two moving belts. The goal of this paper is to describe the effects of processing conditions, such as heater temperature, roller pressure and feed speed, on the quality of the prepreg produced. The quality is defined here in terms of tensile strength and its variability.

EXPERIMENTAL

A schematic of the prepreg machine is shown in Figure 1. It consists of three sections: a supply rack, a heating chamber and a take-up rack. Five rolls are mounted on the supply rack: two parchment paper rolls, two thermoplastic film rolls and a dry fabric tape roll (Figure 2). As they are pulled off of the rolls, the five layers are brought together by a pair of rollers before entering the heating chamber. Two banks of electric heaters, one above and the other below the layered stack, are used to heat the polymer films above their melt temperature as they move through the heating chamber. Inside the heating chamber, the layered stack passes between three pairs of spring-supported rollers, which apply transverse pressure to force the melted polymer into the dry fabric tape. The springs can be changed to vary the pressure exerted by the rollers on the layered material. The parchment paper layers prevent the melted plastic from sticking and accumulating on the rollers. Upon leaving the heating chamber, the prepreg material is collected onto a take-up roll. The process is powered by a variable speed electric motor located in the take-up section.

The materials used in this study are 150 mm wide woven E-glass fabric tape (8.75 oz/yd², plain weave, 2.7 mm thickness) and 150 mm wide polyamide-6 (nylon-6) film. The melting point of polyamide-6 is reported to be 220°C. The process parameters investigated are the heater temperature (310, 320, 330, 350, 360 and 370°C), feed speed (0.3-0.4 m/min and 0.45-0.6 m/min) and spring rate of the roller support springs (0.795, 1.05, 1.32 and 7 N/mm). The lower and upper temperature limits were determined in a trial run by conducting a temperature sweep at each speed. The lower limit was the temperature at which uniform impregnation was visible. The upper limit was the temperature at which charring was visible on the prepreg surface, which indicated polymer degradation. The selection of the spring rates was due to the availability of springs that met the space and geometric constraints. The first feed speed was the slowest the electric motor could run without stalling. The second feed speed was an increase of 50%. The variation of the feed rate is due to an increase in radius of the take up roll as the finished material accumulates. A summary of the process parameters is

shown in Table 1. The highest spring rate was used in a few experiments in the latter part of the investigation.

Figure 1: Schematic of continuous resin infusion process

1: Parchment paper, 2: Nylon film, 3: Dry fabric

Figure 2: Construction of the layered stack used in making the prepreg

Table 1: Process Parameters Matrix

K1: 0.795 T: 310 S1: 0.3-0.4	K1: 0.795 T: 320 S1: 0.3-0.4	K1: 0.795 T: 330 S1: 0.3-0.4	K1: 0.795 T: 350 S2: 0.45-0.6	K1: 0.795 T: 360 S2: 0.45-0.6	K1: 0.795 T: 370 S2: 0.45-0.6
K2: 1.05 T: 310 S1: 0.3-0.4	K2: 1.05 T: 320 S1: 0.3-0.4	K2: 1.05 T: 330 S1: 0.3-0.4	K2: 1.05 T: 350 S2: 0.45-0.6	K2: 1.05 T: 360 S2: 0.45-0.6	K2: 1.05 T: 370 S2: 0.45-0.6
K3: 1.32 T: 310 S1: 0.3-0.4	K3: 1.32 T: 320 S1: 0.3-0.4	K3: 1.32 T: 330 S1: 0.3-0.4	K3: 1.32 T: 350 S2: 0.45-0.6	K3: 1.32 T: 360 S2: 0.45-0.6	K3: 1.32 T: 370 S2: 0.45-0.6

Note: K1, K2 and K3 = spring rates (N/mm), T = heater temperature (°C),
S1 and S2 = feed speed (m/min.)

Approximately 2 meter long of prepreg sheet was produced at each condition. The average fiber volume fraction determined by resin burn out test was 50.2%. Five samples were cut in the weft direction approximately every 300 mm along the prepreg length. Five equally spaced samples were cut across the face of one section parallel to the warp. Tensile strengths of the prepreg were determined using dog-bone shaped specimens machined from the prepreg samples. The average tensile strengths of 5 samples in the weft and 5 samples in the warp directions are reported here for each combination of process conditions.

Figure 3: Location of specimens cut from each processing run.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 4 the average tensile strengths in the warp and weft directions are plotted versus heater temperature at the first three spring rates. It is evident from the data that as the temperature of the heaters was increased, the tensile strength also increased, which can be attributed to the decrease in polymer viscosity at higher temperatures. The level of impregnation, which leads to higher tensile strength, is directly related to decreasing polymer viscosity. The heater temperatures were 310-330°C at 0.3-0.4 m/min. and 350-370°C at 0.45-0.6 m/min. The higher heater temperature was necessary at higher speed to allow the polymer to melt before reaching the first set of compression rollers. The material processed at 370°C had visible brown charred sections indicating polymer degradation. This was also the reason for reduction in tensile strength at 370°C.

Figure 4: Average tensile strength vs. heater temperature at each spring rate for specimens parallel to the warp and parallel to the weft.

Figure 5: Average tensile strength vs. spring rate for specimens parallel to the weft and parallel to the warp at each heater temperature

Figure 5 shows the effect of spring rate on the average tensile strength of the prepregs. The spring rate of the roller support springs controls the transverse pressure on the liquid polymer films as the sandwich material is pulled between the rollers. No consistent trend of the effect of spring rate was observed when the spring rate was increased from 0.795 to 1.05 N/mm; however, in most cases, the tensile strength was lower when the spring rate was increased from 1.05 to 1.32 N/mm. The difference in tensile strength was close enough to suggest that the variations are random and is perhaps more due to natural inhomogeneities in the composite. To examine the effect of high spring rate, several prepreg lengths were manufactured using springs with 7 N/mm spring rate, which was an order of magnitude greater than the lowest spring rate used earlier. As shown in Figure 6, increasing the spring rate reduced the average tensile strength of the prepreg. According to Darcy's law, increasing the transverse pressure increases the level of impregnation and reduces the impregnation time. However, it was also suggested by Nygard et al. [3] and by Peltonen et al. [4] that very high pressures may flatten the yarns, cause them to deform into square cross sections, and compress the filaments in each yarn together. The decrease in permeability due to reduced flow space between the filaments makes resin impregnation and fiber wetting more difficult especially with the higher viscosity of a thermoplastic resin [5, 6].

To evaluate the difference in impregnation between the prepregs produced with the stiffest springs (7 N/mm) and the softest springs (0.795 N/mm), the prepreg cross sections were examined using a scanning electron microscope. The micrographs shown in Figure 7 are cross sections of the prepreg samples cut parallel to the warp at both feed speeds. It is evident from Figure 7 that the prepregs produced with the 7 N/mm springs had very little micro-impregnation of the filaments. The polymer is distinctly visible as just a layer on the surface and the boundary between the filaments and polymer is clearly visible. The prepregs produced with the 0.795 N/mm springs show better impregnation at both feed speeds. Figure 7 does not definitively suggest a reason for the lack of impregnation with the stiffest springs; however, based on the published research on fiber compressibility, it is concluded that the 7 N/mm springs compressed

the filaments in each yarn tightly together which decreased their permeability and the liquid polymer achieved little to no micro flow.

Figure 6: Average tensile strengths of preregs produced at different spring rates

(a) 0.3-0.4 m/min., 7 N/mm

(b) 0.3-0.4 m/min., 0.795 N/mm

(c) 0.45-0.6 m/min., 7 N/mm

(d) 0.45-0.6 m/min., 0.795 N/mm

Figure 7: SEM photographs of prepreg cross sections

Figure 8: Prepreg thickness distribution

The effect of the process parameters on prepreg thickness also evaluated. For each set of processing conditions, the thickness of a group of 5 specimens was measured to determine the average thickness. The number of occurrences of each thickness is plotted in Figure 8. The data shows that the thickness of the prepreg ranged between 0.34 and 0.44 mm, with an average value of approximately 0.4 mm. The total initial thickness of the materials prior to processing was 2.72 mm. The difference between the initial thickness and the prepreg thickness suggests that significant compression of the fabric network took place.

In terms of the spatial distribution of tensile strengths, it was observed that in the warp direction, the tensile strength of the two outer specimens was higher than the three inner specimens. A few examples of this trend are plotted in Figure 9. This can be attributed to two factors. Due to variations within the yarn layout of the fabric tape, the yarns at the edges of the tape were packed more tightly than at the center. The other factor that may have contributed to the increased strength was a slightly higher temperature at the outer edges of the prepreg due to a concentration of heat where the heaters overlapped the edges of the material. Thus, the polymer was able to better impregnate the fibers in the outer specimens, which also contributed to their increased strength. This variation can be controlled by reducing the outer heater temperature by 1-5 degrees or by repositioning outer heater bands by a few millimeters so that the heat distribution is more consistent across the face of the prepreg and there is no concentrated heat at the edges.

For the specimens parallel to the weft, the tensile strength was consistent. This shows that the level of impregnation along the length of the prepreg was consistent, and thus specimens cut parallel to the weft from displayed similar tensile properties. Examples of the consistency of the specimens parallel to the weft are shown below in Figure 10 where the curves are almost flat.

Figure 9: Tensile strength of specimens parallel to the warp. 1 and 5 represent specimens at the edges, 3 at the center, and 2 and 4 next to the center

Figure 10: Tensile strength of weft specimens at 300 mm intervals along the prepreg length

CONCLUSIONS

Based solely on tensile strength and its distribution, the conclusion can be drawn that continuous resin infusion using compression rollers can produce uniform quality prepreg provided proper processing conditions are used. At elevated temperatures, degradation of the polymer is more likely and the difference in impregnation at lower temperatures was not significant enough to warrant very higher temperatures being used. The recommended operation temperature should be just high enough to promote mechanical adhesion and macro flow around the yarns. Tensile testing also suggested that high spring rate can cause decrease in tensile strength, which is attributed to reduced micro-impregnation caused by flattening and reduced flow space between the

filaments. Softer springs also allow any wrinkle, loose fiber, or particular contamination to pass between the compression rollers instead of getting stuck and stalling the process. It is also recommended that the feed speed be run as slow as possible. The frequency of physical defects increased with increased feed speed. This also allows the use of a lower heater temperature.

References

1. X. Wang, C. Mayer, and M. Neitzel, Some Issues on Impregnation in Manufacturing of Thermoplastic Composites by Using a Double Belt Press, *Polymer Composites*, 1997, 18:701-710.
2. C. Mayer, X. Wang, and M. Neitzel, Macro- and Micro-impregnation Phenomena in Continuous Manufacturing of Fabric Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites, *Composites: Part A*, 1998, 29:783-793.
3. P. Nygard and C.-G. Gustafson, Continuous Glass Fiber-Polypropylene Composites made by Melt Impregnation, *J. Thermoplastic Composites*, 2004, 17:167-184
4. P. Peltonen, L. Lahteenkorva, E. J. Paakonen, P. K. Jarvela and P. Tormala, The Influence of Melt Impregnation on the Degree of Impregnation of a Polypropylene/Glass Fiber Prepreg, *J. Thermoplastic Composites*, 1992, 5:318-343.
5. P. J. Bates, D. Taylor and M. F. Cunningham, Compaction and Transverse Permeability of Glass Rovings, *Applied Composite Materials*, 2001, 8:163-178.
6. C. Visconti, A. Langella and M. Durante, Analysis of Transversal Permeability for Different Types of Glass Fiber Reinforcement, *Applied Composite Materials*, 2003, 10: 119-127.